

THE IMPORTANCE OF ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION IN SOLVING
MODERN ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS

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Annotation: *This article addresses the issues of the relationship between man and nature as solutions to environmental problems and ways to overcome them. The students' questionnaires were also used to determine their environmental literacy, worldview, and knowledge of the environment through experiments. The scientific researches of the scientists on the problems of the subject were analyzed and pedagogically compared.*

Keywords: *ecology, environment, nature, human, physical education, education, problem, activity, potential, student, teacher, social, environmental threat, concept, problem, opportunity, solution, relevance, environmental crisis, climate change, higher educational institution.*

Relevance of the research topic. One of the most important areas of modern restructuring of school natural science education is its humanization, which involves familiarizing students with the most important problems of the modern world. The main one is the ecological problem.

The development of the scientific and technological revolution, the industrialization of most types of production becomes dominant, as a result of which the impact of human activity on the biosphere becomes global. The equilibria that have developed in nature for millennia are shifting. There are processes (biological, chemical, physical, technical and technological) pollution of the atmosphere, hydrosphere, lithosphere of the Earth, biosphere and near space. All of this makes the Earth's environment uninhabitable. On the face of an impending ecological catastrophe, which consists in the formation of alien processes in natural cycles in the Biosphere, the complete disappearance and threat of extinction of many species of animals and plants, natural resources necessary for the development of the productive forces of society, an energy crisis.

Environmental problems are complex and depend on many factors, including social ones. One of the most important is the pedagogical and educational, which consists in the need to familiarize the broad strata of the population and, above all, young people, with the listed environmental problems, the formation of ecological consciousness and thinking, which presuppose an understanding of the need and moral need for the protection of nature and rational use of natural resources. The pedagogical aspect of solving environmental problems, in particular, includes: systems of knowledge about nature, society, principles of nature management, assessing the results and consequences of interaction between society and nature, ways to optimize this interaction; systems of

intellectual and practical skills and habits for the protection of nature and the rational use of its resources; experience of creative activity in the study and practical participation in the protection of the natural environment; systems of moral norms, manifested in the evaluative and emotional attitude to the natural environment.

The university has an important place in environmental education and education. The new Concept for the development of universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the humanization of higher education institutions put the ecological education of the younger generation on one of the important places in the goals and methods of achieving it, open up large, fundamentally new opportunities for this. The preparation of a comprehensively developed, self-developing personality, and this is precisely what is put in the priorities of the goals of modern school education, is inseparable from the understanding of the global environmental problems of our time around the world and native land. Understanding the social and personal significance of preventing acute environmental situations is the basis of moral involvement in everything that surrounds, personal responsibility for the future of our people, the whole world, provides an active life position. Introducing students to these problems is a powerful source of instilling feelings of international solidarity, the culture of interethnic relations. The use of environmental issues in the labor training of students allows to revive the deep national traditions of the Uzbek people for the protection of the natural environment of their native land, a careful attitude towards it.

The inter-scientific nature of environmental problems, their complexity opens up wide opportunities for this, while, of course, one of the central places in this work, along with other academic subjects of the natural science cycle, rightfully belongs to the course of biology. This is due to the fact that the main object of ecology is wildlife.

There are a large number of complex biological systems in the biosphere of the Earth; the constancy and variability of species, populations of biogeocenosis are determined by biological, chemical, physical, technical, social factors.

The basis of the biological content of ecological upbringing and education is the knowledge of living natural systems, the conditions for their stability, the role of the anthropogenic factor in ensuring the integrity and stability of living systems of their life.

The range of environmental issues in the content of higher education also includes: the dependence of the course of processes in living systems on external factors, the habitat of living organisms. With the disclosure of the meaning of the anthropogenic factor, the concept of "biological pollution", its conditions (physical, chemical, technical factors), sources, optimization issues (waste-free production, closed biological, technological cycles, environmentally friendly energy sources, their rational use, creation of artificial food).

The degree of elaboration of the problem. General pedagogical aspects of the problem of ecological upbringing and education of universities are disclosed in the works of I.D. Zverev, I.T. Suravegina, E.A. Turdikulova, A.P. Zakhlebny, I.T. Ponamareva. They established general approaches and principles of developing the content of ecological education and upbringing, studied the pedagogical conditions for its implementation in the process of teaching higher educational disciplines. Research by I.T.

Suravegina, Ya.I. Gabeva, M.A.Zaitseva, G.S. Kalinova, A.I. Bugaev, I.D. Zverev, M.Nazarov is devoted to environmental education in higher educational institutions. I., Turdikulov E.A., Krasnovidova S.S., Mamatova A.N., Reznikova V.Z., Traitak D.I., Shapokene E.Yu., Mukhammadiev K.B. They revealed peculiarities of the content of ecological knowledge, skills and abilities related $\rightarrow$ some methodological features and methods of formation of students' ecological knowledge and beliefs are considered. However, it should be emphasized that the concrete-substantive basis of these studies cannot be mechanically transferred and used in schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan, since they do not take into account the regional and socio-economic characteristics of the Republic. In addition, most of these studies are based on the content of the programs and do not take into account many modern opportunities that open up new opportunities in the environmental education of students [1].

The analysis of the methodological literature showed that there are still no methodological manuals and recommendations devoted to the study of the possibilities and methods of reflecting environmental issues in the universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These issues have not yet found a worthy systematic reflection in the textbooks of universities and recommendations for teachers. Research is needed, in which these issues should be reflected both in the core and in universities of education for the Republic, associated with global, regional and local features of the environmental problems of the Central Asian region, since their nature is different in different regions, due to different climatic and geographical conditions, the predominant development of certain types of industries, due to economic, national and historical characteristics.

The dominant sectors of the national economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan are cotton growing, animal husbandry, vegetable growing, sericulture. Ecological problems in these branches of agriculture of the republic are becoming more and more aggravated every year, a large amount of mineral fertilizers, herbicides, defoliant is used, which, on the one hand, significantly reduces the cost of products, and on the other hand, in the context of an increase in the expansion of field treatments with chemicals leads to chemical pollution of the environment, death of animals and plants, which negatively affects the human body [2].

The consequence of the methodological and pedagogical underdevelopment of these problems is that, as our research has shown (it was studied by the universities of the Tashkent, Khorezm, Karakalpak regions), the ecological aspects of education of students in teaching biology are not yet taken into account by teachers. In turn, students do not possess the necessary environmental knowledge and skills, demonstrate their low level, are not familiar with the methods and measures to prevent and protect against the harmful effects of the substances used on the human body, animals and plants [3].

Research problem consists in overcoming the contradiction between the objective necessity of society in ecologically literate workers with ecological consciousness, thinking and culture of behavior, and the theoretical and practical underdevelopment of the system of ecological education of students in the universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the educational process.

Object of study – educational and related socially useful activities of students in the universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Subject of study – the process of environmental education of students during lessons and after school hours.

Purpose of the study – to develop the content and pedagogical conditions of ecological education of students of the University of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the educational process of physical education in the classroom and after school hours.

Research hypothesis: environmental education of students of Uzbekistan in the process of teaching physical education will be effective if:

– in terms of content, it will take into account regional, local history, historical, national and human characteristics of the region's environmental problems;

– when studying environmental issues, an interdisciplinary connection between physical education and academic subjects will be provided natural science cycle (chemistry, geography and physics);

– practical orientation of disclosure will be provided ecological materials in teaching physical education to use their connection in the labor socially useful activity of students.

We also assume that the developed methodology of ecological education will help improve the quality of knowledge and skills of students in physical education in other natural science disciplines.

Research objectives:

1. Determination of the main directions, principles and pedagogical conditions of ecological education of students in the process of teaching physical education.

2. Selection of the content and establishment of the volume of questions that reveal regional, historical, national, local lore aspects of environmental problems associated with the subjects of physical education.

3. Development of the content and structure of intersubject connections of ecological orientation for physical education of the course of biology with courses of chemistry, physics and geography.

4. Establishment of the basic pedagogical conditions of ecological education of universities in the process of teaching physical education in the classroom and after school hours.

5. Verification of the effectiveness of the developed methodology in experimental work.

6. Development of guidelines.

Methodological framework studies have made philosophical works on the dialectics of the relationship between human society and nature, upbringing and education of the younger generation, more connected with the issue of nature protection and rational use of its resources, with modern tasks of restructuring public education in a democratization and socio-economic development of society.

Research method:

– study of philosophical and socio-psychological literature on the problems of

interaction between society and nature;

- study and analysis of scientific literature on environmental problems; arising in the conditions of intensive development of various branches of the national economy;

- analysis of textbooks, teaching aids and recommendations, articles on environmental education and training;

- observation and analysis of the educational process in physical education, conducting tests, questioning students and teachers, conducting conversations with them;

- study of the advanced experience of ecological education of students of secondary schools;

- conducting a pedagogical experiment and analyzing its results.

The scientific novelty of the research lies in the fact that it contains:

- the features of ecological education of students of rural schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan are revealed when teaching physical education on an interdisciplinary basis;

- the content and pedagogical conditions of ecological education of students in teaching physical education at the university have been developed, taking into account: local history and regional approach, interdisciplinary communication, practical orientation of students' education.

The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that its results made it possible to formulate important ideas, conclusions and recommendations for the ecological education of students when teaching physical education, their application in teaching practice physical education increases the level of students' ecological consciousness and their ecological culture, develops the necessary ecological skills and abilities; associated with work, leads to an improvement in the quality of knowledge and skills of students on programmatic issues of physical education. The findings and recommendations were brought to the level of their practical use by teachers. They can also be useful to teachers of the corresponding departments of pedagogical universities and universities, authors of textbooks, teaching and methodological manuals on the problems of environmental education and upbringing.

The following are submitted for defense:

1. The main directions, ways and principles of improving the ecological education of students in teaching physical education.

2. The provision that the environmental education of students in teaching physical education should be based on local history, regional basis and rely on interdisciplinary connections and practical orientation of education.

3. Methods of ecological education of students in the process of teaching physical education.

4. Results of the pedagogical experiment.

5. Development of guidelines.

Approbation of the study. The developed methodology of environmental education of students in the process of teaching physical education has passed an extended experimental test in 3 universities of the Republic: Tashkent State University of

Transport, Gulistan State Pedagogical University, Samarkand State University. About 700 students were covered.

During the research, its results were periodically reported and discussed:

- Republican conference on environmental education and upbringing (Tashkent, 2019);
- Regional conference on environmental education and upbringing of students (Tashkent, 2020);
- at the district methodological associations, teachers of the Tashkent region (periodically from 2018 to 2020);

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